

Supporting Information

Directional formation of microtubes by soft-template electropolymerization from fully conjugated triphenylamine-based monomers

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Experimental section

Monomer synthesis and characterization.

Tris(4-(thiophen-2-yl)phenyl)amine(**N-Ph-2-Th**) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Tris(4-bromophenyl)amine and all the used boronic acids were purchased from TCI. The other original monomers were synthesized from tris(4-bromophenyl)amine and by three Suzuki reactions as shown in Scheme S1. The components used for the Suzuki reaction were tris(4-bromophenyl)amine (2 mmol, 1.0 eq.), the corresponding boronic acid (7.0 mmol, 3.5 eq.), tetrakis(triphenylphosphine)-

palladium(0) (0.1 mmol, 0.1 eq.) and sodium carbonate (4.0 g). These components were mixed to a solution containing 100 mL of toluene, 20 mL of ethanol and 10 mL of water, and were refluxed for 3 days. After solvent evaporation, the crude products were purified by column chromatography (silica gel; eluent: petroleum ether).

NMR spectra were obtained with a 400 MHz ultra blinded spectrometer equipped with an AVANCE III Nano HD electronic console. The proton and carbon frequencies were 400.13MHz and 100.63MHz, respectively.

Scheme S1. Synthesis of original monomers by Suzuki reaction.

Tris(4-(thiophen-3-yl)phenyl)amine (N-Ph-3-Th).

Yield: 23%.

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (400MHz, CDCl_3); δ (ppm): 7.50 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 6H), 7.38 (m, 9H) 7.18 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 6H).

$^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 146.47, 141.82, 130.56, 127.28, 126.17, 126.13, 124.36, 119.38.

Tris(4'-(9H-carbazol-9-yl)-[1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl)amine(N-Ph-p-Cb).

Yield: 13%.

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 8.17 (d, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 6H), 7.91 (d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, 6H), 7.80 (m, 3H), 7.71 (d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, 6H), 7.62 (m, 6H), 7.51 (m, 6H), 7.46 (m, 9H), 7.32 (m, 6H).

$^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 146.80, 140.82, 139.52, 139.28, 137.25, 136.60, 135.00, 132.46, 128.50, 128.00, 127.48, 126.01, 123.50, 120.37, 120.00, 109.82.

Tris(3'-(9H-carbazol-9-yl)-[1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl)amine (N-Ph-m-Cb).

Yield: 49%.

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 8.17 (d, $J = 7.7$ Hz Hz, 6H), 7.80 (m, 3H), 7.65 (m, 6H), 7.57 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 6H), 7.54 (m, 3H), 7.49 (m, 6H), 7.42 (m, 6H), 7.31 (m, 6H), 7.26 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 6H).

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 147.08, 142.40, 140.87, 138.23, 134.69, 130.25, 128.02, 125.95, 125.62, 125.54, 124.54, 123.39, 120.32, 120.00, 109.80.

Tris(2'-(9*H*-carbazol-9-yl)-[1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl)amine (N-Ph-o-Cb).

Yield: 77%.

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 7.98 (d, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 6H), 7.50 (m, 12H), 7.20 (m, 6H), 7.02 (m, 12H), 6.58 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 6H), 5.95 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 6H).

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 146.14, 140.88, 140.39, 134.75, 132.62, 130.81, 129.67, 128.64, 128.26, 125.49, 123.32, 123.00, 119.92, 119.34, 110.00.

Tris(4-(thiophen-3-yl)phenyl)amine (N-Ph-3-Th).

Yield: 23%.

^1H NMR (400MHz, CDCl_3); δ (ppm): 7.50 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 6H), 7.38 (m, 9H) 7.18 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 6H).

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 146.47, 141.82, 130.56, 127.28, 126.17, 126.13, 124.36, 119.38.

Computational methodology.

All the computational studies were performed with Gaussian 16 package of programs¹ using the density functional theory method (DFT). The hybrid functional B3LYP, which combines Becke's three-parameter hybrid exchange functional²³ and Lee–Yang–Parr's gradient-corrected correlation functional,⁴ and 6-31G split valence basis set supplemented by d-polarization functions were used for geometry optimizations of isolated molecules in a gas phase. No constraints were used, and all structures were free to optimize. The force constants and vibrational frequency analysis for stationary points have been calculated after optimizations to check that they are true energy minima.

Electronic structure for the optimized geometries were calculated at the same level of theory. The restricted Hartree-Fock formalism was used for the neutral states of the molecules, and unrestricted Hartree-Fock formalism was used for radical cation calculations.

Visualization of the orbital coefficients and spin density distribution (in radical cations) were performed with GaussView 6.0 software.

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Soft-template electropolymerization.

Two solvents were investigated: dichloromethane (CH_2Cl_2) and dichloromethane saturated with water ($\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ sat.). Because the solubility of water in dichloromethane is ultra-low, the later was very easily prepared by mixing water and dichloromethane, and after decantation the aqueous phase was discarded. Tetrabutylammonium perchlorate (Bu_4NClO_4) (0.1 M) as the supporting electrolyte and monomer (0.005 M) were added to the solvent. Three electrodes were connected to an Autolab potentiostat-galvanostat model PGSTAT100 (Metrohm). 2 cm^2 gold-coated silicon wafer as the working electrode, glassy carbon rod as the counter-electrode, and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as the reference electrode. First, the oxidation potential for each monomer were determined by cyclic voltammetry. Then, two electrodeposition methods were investigated (by cyclic voltammetry and at constant potential). The experiments by cyclic voltammetry were performed from -1 V to E^{ox} , at a scan rate of 20 mV s^{-1} with different numbers of scans (1, 3 and 5). The experiments at constant potential were performed with a potential $E = E^{\text{ox}}$, and with different deposition charges ($12.5, 25, 50, 100, 200$ and 400 mC cm^{-2}). Then, the substrates were abundantly washed with CH_2Cl_2 .

Smooth surfaces with each monomer were prepared using a two-step process. First deposition at constant potential with a low deposition charge of 1 mC cm^{-2} . Then, in order to have polymers in the same state (i.e. dedoped state) as in cyclic voltammetry experiments, the deposits were reduced with one back scan from E^{ox} to -1 V in a solution free of monomer.

Surface characterization.

Samples were observed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) prior to electrodeposition using a JEOL JSM-1400 TEM. For imaging, a drop of $0.45 \mu\text{m}$ -filtered solution was deposited onto a 400 mesh TEM copper grid with a carbon support film and the exceeding liquid was absorbed with a paper filter to avoid excessive salt deposition onto the TEM grids.

The surface structures were imaged with a JEOL JSM-6700F scanning electron microscope (SEM). The surface wettability was characterized by measuring apparent contact angles (θ) using a KRÜSS DSA30 goniometer. Three probes of liquids of different surface tensions (γ_{LV}) were used: water (72.8 mN/m), diiodomethane (50.0 mN/m) and *n*-hexadecane (27.6 mN/m).

Each value is given here is a mean value of five measurements. For characterizing the water adhesion, a water droplet was placed on the substrate and the substrate was inclined until the droplet moved. If the droplet moved, that indicated extremely high water adhesion (parahydrophobic or sticky superhydrophobic). For smooth surfaces, the apparent contact angles are called Young' angles (θ^{Y}). Their surface energy γ_{SV} were calculated with the Owens-Wendt equation as well as their polar ($\gamma_{\text{SV,P}}$) and dispersive ($\gamma_{\text{SV,D}}$) parts.

Figure S1. B3LYP/6-31G(d) optimized geometries of studied monomers in a gas phase. For clarity, two views of each structure are shown, i.e. perpendicular to the triphenylamine plane and in the plane.

Figure S2. Orbital coefficients distribution in studied monomers, from HOMO-3 to LUMO+3 orbitals, calculated at B3LYP/6-31G(d) level in a gas phase.

Electrochemical characterization

Figure S3. Cyclic voltammograms of studied compounds on cycling. Electrodepositions were performed in CH_2Cl_2 or $(\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O sat.})$ as solvents and with 0.1 M of Bu_4NClO_4 as an electrolyte. The range of potential scans was from -1 V to E^{ox} , scan rate 20 mV s^{-1} . First five scans are shown.

1 scan

3 scans

5 scans

Figure S4. SEM images of electrodeposited surfaces from **N-Ph-3-Th** by CV in ($\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ sat.) with 0.1 M of Bu_4NClO_4 for 1, 3 and 5 scans in the potential range from -1 V to E^{ox} at the scan rate of 20 mV s^{-1} . Magnification is $\times 10,000$.

Figure S5. Potentiostatic electrodeposition of studied monomers at applied potentials E^{ox} (currents vs time curves at constant potential E^{ox} are shown) in CH_2Cl_2 or ($\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O sat.}$) as solvents, with 0.1 M of Bu_4NClO_4 as an electrolyte.

Figure S6. ^1H NMR spectrum of N-Ph-3-Th in CDCl_3 .

Figure S7. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of N-Ph-3-Th in CDCl_3 .

Figure S8. ^1H NMR spectrum of N-Ph-p-Cb in CDCl_3 .

Figure S9. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of N-Ph-p-Cb in CDCl_3 .

Figure S10. ^1H NMR spectrum of N-Ph-m-Cb in CDCl_3 .

Figure S11. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of N-Ph-m-Cb in CDCl_3 .

Figure S12. ¹H NMR spectrum of N-Ph-o-Cb in CDCl₃.

Figure S13. ¹³C NMR spectrum of N-Ph-o-Cb in CDCl₃.

N-Ph-2-Th, neutral state $E_{\text{total}} = -2405.1372798$ Hartree // B3LYP/6-31G(d)

C	1.41497900	-0.12292300	0.14377400
N	0.00032700	-0.00013300	0.14659600
C	-0.60070000	1.28641800	0.14391700
C	-0.81348000	-1.16378600	0.14388000
C	-1.73092900	1.55370200	0.93437100
C	-2.32506800	2.80925900	0.91876300
C	-1.80261700	3.85995300	0.14117500
C	-0.66527400	3.58302100	-0.63884100
C	-0.08185500	2.32165300	-0.65016600
C	-1.97002400	-1.23141000	-0.64942800
C	-2.77098000	-2.36713900	-0.63803000
C	-2.44189900	-3.49102200	0.14125200
C	-1.27020500	-3.41876800	0.91807600
C	-0.47962400	-2.27666200	0.93365200
C	2.05192000	-1.09112300	-0.64896200
C	3.43600600	-1.21651600	-0.63780100
C	4.24472300	-0.36887400	0.14074900
C	3.59621000	0.61011700	0.91697500
C	2.21181100	0.72342900	0.93274500
C	-2.42935500	5.18565500	0.15997600
C	-3.27691500	-4.69643100	0.16006100
C	5.70617900	-0.48894400	0.15950300
C	-3.18344000	5.76561300	1.15589100
C	-3.64480100	7.07590300	0.83919200
C	-3.24256100	7.49574700	-0.39848100
S	-2.29594400	6.28534400	-1.20312200
C	-3.40183100	-5.63989700	1.15560900
C	-4.30631200	-6.69423100	0.83890700
C	-4.87163000	-6.55511900	-0.39840900
S	-4.29680600	-5.12988800	-1.20270800
C	6.58564300	-0.12411100	1.15463600
C	7.95101800	-0.38021300	0.83816000
C	8.11331100	-0.94062100	-0.39856800
S	6.59163800	-1.15666600	-1.20259600
H	-2.14950800	0.76597100	1.55249500
H	-3.21533100	2.97833800	1.51713400
H	-0.22549300	4.36937700	-1.24633000
H	0.78850400	2.13509400	-1.27090400
H	-2.24389000	-0.38400300	-1.26954300
H	-3.67233500	-2.37889700	-1.24484500
H	-0.97135800	-4.27458400	1.51597700
H	0.41222800	-2.24579500	1.55127400
H	1.45505400	-1.75256100	-1.26854800
H	3.89694600	-1.99151100	-1.24420400
H	4.18791200	1.29742400	1.51422500
H	1.73916000	1.48074500	1.54988900
H	-3.37815400	5.27709400	2.10452400
H	-4.24321500	7.68239900	1.51066200
H	-3.44453700	8.43876900	-0.88833500
H	-2.88090500	-5.56483900	2.10401400
H	-4.53218600	-7.51596800	1.51012900
H	-5.58775600	-7.20114500	-0.88815600
H	6.26007300	0.29041600	2.10260400
H	8.77556400	-0.16403800	1.50913200
H	9.03091200	-1.23807200	-0.88803000

N-Ph-3-Th, neutral state $E_{\text{total}} = -2405.1346219$ Hartree // B3LYP/6-31G(d)

C	1.04840400	-0.95887100	-0.01410000
N	-0.00272300	-0.00384200	0.01441600
C	0.29836800	1.38430200	0.03065400
C	-1.35540100	-0.43726800	0.03069200
C	-0.42265800	2.26714400	0.85019500
C	-0.13023500	3.62682000	0.85490200
C	0.90131100	4.15982300	0.06309300
C	1.62633100	3.26368300	-0.74138200
C	1.32676800	1.90658500	-0.77077900
C	-2.33080100	0.22126500	-0.73587300
C	-3.65566800	-0.19845500	-0.70641200
C	-4.06050200	-1.30302300	0.06294700
C	-3.07439900	-1.95845100	0.82001700
C	-1.75056700	-1.53221100	0.81550600
C	0.95776100	-2.10402500	-0.82124700
C	1.98542500	-3.04091800	-0.83824600
C	3.15070000	-2.86820100	-0.07174400
C	3.23665500	-1.71003300	0.72010800
C	2.20514400	-0.77911500	0.76199400
C	1.20451200	5.60474800	0.07538600
C	-5.46345900	-1.76290000	0.07456300
C	4.23636000	-3.86850900	-0.09664100
C	1.00340900	6.46513200	1.21190300
C	1.35682200	7.76240000	0.98182700
S	1.94590400	7.98430000	-0.63566000
C	1.71243500	6.30638400	-0.99423100
C	-6.09525000	-2.40830000	1.19558100
C	-7.39815700	-2.74211100	0.96810600
S	-7.90321800	-2.28402300	-0.62801200
C	-6.33723400	-1.63475800	-0.98112100
C	4.54922500	-4.69655400	-1.23190500
C	5.59479100	-5.54534100	-1.01489600
S	6.23594400	-5.36855000	0.58828500
C	5.07888100	-4.13463800	0.95868000
H	-1.21981100	1.88280200	1.47846100
H	-0.72192100	4.28797400	1.48179800
H	2.44641600	3.63499200	-1.34965200
H	1.89840300	1.23979300	-1.40837600
H	-2.04613600	1.07244600	-1.34607700
H	-4.39398200	0.34805400	-1.28659800
H	-3.34435300	-2.82368500	1.41893400
H	-1.01222400	-2.05316700	1.41661100
H	0.07295400	-2.26018700	-1.43001700
H	1.87514900	-3.92862800	-1.45471000
H	4.13218200	-1.53015900	1.30838600
H	2.29625800	0.10167900	1.38951400
H	0.63749300	6.11281600	2.17005000
H	1.32297900	8.59742300	1.66850300
H	1.92719300	5.93499200	-1.98693500
H	-5.59628300	-2.58398700	2.14227700
H	-8.09669000	-3.21363600	1.64607800
H	-6.13418900	-1.22710000	-1.96199100
H	4.02739600	-4.63131000	-2.18032400
H	6.03817800	-6.25134800	-1.70402000
H	5.05813700	-3.69811800	1.94789200

N-Ph-p-Cb, neutral state $E_{\text{total}} = -2991.6888124$ Hartree // B3LYP/6-31G(d)

C	1.23474800	-0.70156900	-0.00262200
N	0.00009600	-0.00047300	-0.00314600
C	-0.01005500	1.41933900	-0.00280800
C	-1.22442900	-0.71914100	-0.00273600
C	-0.92383600	2.13124900	0.79100500
C	-0.93436700	3.52145900	0.78185000
C	-0.03029900	4.25940700	-0.00215900
C	0.88420000	3.53478600	-0.78652100
C	0.89348200	2.14456400	-0.79630800
C	-2.30439300	-0.29899400	-0.79593100
C	-3.50382800	-1.00194700	-0.78591500
C	-3.67407800	-2.15638100	-0.00174000
C	-2.58279200	-2.57068700	0.78185400
C	-1.38400900	-1.86660600	0.79085800
C	2.30823000	-0.26573600	0.79085700
C	3.51749800	-0.95165400	0.78183900
C	3.70443100	-2.10400000	-0.00158300
C	2.61955200	-2.53410700	-0.78557500
C	1.41095800	-1.84702800	-0.79560800
C	-4.95194400	-2.90602000	-0.00113900
C	-0.04078000	5.74088000	-0.00167800
C	4.99273900	-2.83554700	-0.00102800
C	-6.18623900	-2.24213300	-0.11445700
C	-7.38942900	-2.94137800	-0.10674700
C	-7.39299900	-4.33794700	0.00002000
C	-6.17216600	-5.01626200	0.10618700
C	-4.97468800	-4.30727700	0.11276900
C	1.15116700	6.47801900	-0.11527100
C	1.14700700	7.86962900	-0.10741700
C	-0.06073000	8.57086100	-0.00031100
C	-1.25847100	7.85257800	0.10607400
C	-1.24301600	6.46103900	0.11254700
C	5.03523700	-4.23647000	-0.11341200
C	6.24257600	-4.92851700	-0.10574200
C	7.45370300	-4.23295100	0.00000000
C	7.43042400	-2.83645500	0.10527000
C	6.21750700	-2.15421500	0.111193600
N	-8.61701800	-5.05597500	0.00062200
N	-0.07072000	9.98990400	0.00045000
N	8.68773500	-4.93363500	0.00056000
C	-9.03489700	-5.96304300	0.98244500
C	-10.31089400	-6.47059300	0.62794700
C	-10.67911300	-5.84395000	-0.62447200
C	-9.61351600	-4.97834000	-0.98036400
C	-0.64758600	10.80514300	0.98228000
C	-0.44937000	12.16402400	0.62791300
C	0.27756900	12.16984400	-0.62442400
C	0.49470700	10.81427400	-0.98041500
C	9.68272400	-4.84076300	0.98175100
C	10.76034100	-5.69203400	0.62747700
C	10.40127700	-6.32552400	-0.62416200
C	9.11847800	-5.83624600	-0.97980700
C	-8.39949500	-6.34439700	2.16753100
C	-9.05316100	-7.26153200	2.98787500
C	-10.31135100	-7.78556000	2.64467000
C	-10.94529100	-7.39137900	1.47000200
C	-11.79314400	-5.94853500	-1.46551300
C	-11.82865200	-5.20353500	-2.64059400
C	-10.75735100	-4.36151200	-2.98520100
C	-9.63713700	-4.23830200	-2.16586300
C	11.04869000	-7.23861300	-1.46468300
C	10.42069500	-7.64321200	-2.63900800
C	9.15547500	-7.13717400	-2.98338300
C	8.48885000	-6.22805000	-2.16455900
C	9.69565100	-4.09874000	2.16613800
C	10.81718100	-4.20519700	2.98602200
C	11.90019200	-5.03278100	2.64301600

C	11.87543500	-5.77993400	1.46902600
C	-1.29555200	10.44534200	2.16729200
C	-1.76319800	11.46984700	2.98770200
C	-1.58817800	12.82155000	2.64461200
C	-0.92984600	13.17367500	1.47000100
C	0.74388200	13.18710200	-1.46530800
C	1.40705800	12.84559800	-2.64033000
C	1.60092100	11.49688200	-2.98504300
C	1.14760900	10.46496700	-2.16587700
H	-1.61771900	1.58830800	1.42470100
H	-1.63200100	4.04468400	1.42980000
H	1.57433000	4.06821400	-1.43420800
H	1.59503300	1.61183400	-1.43024200
H	-2.19385800	0.57504400	-1.42971200
H	-4.31094700	-0.67072700	-1.43333200
H	-2.68702700	-3.43658800	1.42967400
H	-0.56673600	-2.19628300	1.42427700
H	2.18497200	0.60695200	1.42414300
H	4.31954600	-0.60871100	1.42946600
H	2.73638800	-3.39880500	-1.43285000
H	0.59876100	-2.18847500	-1.42932400
H	-6.20732900	-1.15750200	-0.16840600
H	-8.33316100	-2.40763400	-0.16061900
H	-6.16676300	-6.10043700	0.16048000
H	-4.03819700	-4.85491900	0.16628400
H	2.10108400	5.95408000	-0.16953600
H	2.08103300	8.42015400	-0.16143800
H	-2.20016400	8.38985400	0.16061700
H	-2.18545400	5.92370700	0.16626700
H	4.10656800	-4.79729600	-0.16662200
H	6.25244300	-6.01271800	-0.15882400
H	8.36653100	-2.28941500	0.15876700
H	6.22326000	-1.06933800	0.16477100
H	-7.43304400	-5.93686500	2.44500700
H	-8.57817600	-7.57404900	3.91395800
H	-10.79330700	-8.50057300	3.30532600
H	-11.92299200	-7.78933600	1.21076200
H	-12.61753900	-6.60738000	-1.20519400
H	-12.68851100	-5.27547300	-3.30048900
H	-10.79898200	-3.79494600	-3.91158000
H	-8.80989200	-3.59394900	-2.44438500
H	12.03172500	-7.62258500	-1.20453400
H	10.91276700	-8.35239600	-3.29848800
H	8.68520100	-7.45755000	-3.90918400
H	7.51693900	-5.83435700	-2.44293700
H	8.85943800	-3.46553200	2.44343200
H	10.85060800	-3.63674800	3.91157900
H	12.76073700	-5.09180200	3.30329400
H	12.70897500	-6.42766100	1.20993200
H	-1.42568600	9.40456100	2.44467200
H	-2.27133100	11.21457400	3.91374000
H	-1.96659100	13.59631900	3.30531600
H	-0.78578300	14.21940600	1.21084000
H	0.58527200	14.23041100	-1.20488900
H	1.77462800	13.62635900	-3.30009800
H	2.11257100	11.24984600	-3.91137700
H	1.29224800	9.42644600	-2.44453300

N-Ph-m-Cb, neutral state $E_{\text{total}} = -2991.688235$ Hartree // B3LYP/6-31G(d)

C	-0.10834200	1.41542500	-0.16114100
N	0.00071200	-0.00024600	-0.15937400
C	1.28125700	-0.61357900	-0.16034500
C	-1.17081900	-0.80238400	-0.16034000
C	1.53539600	-1.74493200	-0.95232500
C	2.78908800	-2.34584200	-0.94359800
C	3.84233100	-1.83892600	-0.16290900
C	3.57766900	-0.70104700	0.61864300
C	2.32308700	-0.10210400	0.63009800
C	-1.24898600	-1.96051500	0.62992700
C	-2.39544200	-2.74690700	0.61894200
C	-3.51340500	-2.40639600	-0.16190700
C	-3.42545100	-1.24093800	-0.94277900
C	-2.27782600	-0.45625600	-0.95192100
C	0.74399200	2.20095400	-0.95384100
C	0.63778200	3.58715500	-0.94542100
C	-0.32724200	4.24612700	-0.16427700
C	-1.17990300	3.44827800	0.61804700
C	-1.07161400	2.06228300	0.62973000
C	-4.73737700	-3.24383700	-0.16332300
C	5.17987600	-2.47958300	-0.16476300
C	-0.44140600	5.72476700	-0.16650100
C	-4.64884900	-4.64182600	-0.06687100
C	-5.79796000	-5.43849800	-0.06236300
C	-7.06182500	-4.84619500	-0.17108600
C	-7.15804600	-3.46008600	-0.28779000
C	-6.01364900	-2.66510500	-0.27671200
C	6.34615900	-1.70370200	-0.06791400
C	7.61080800	-2.30021400	-0.06322900
C	7.73019400	-3.69081400	-0.17252500
C	6.57811600	-4.46737300	-0.29007700
C	5.31727500	-3.87408300	-0.27914700
C	-1.69666600	6.34637400	-0.06873000
C	-1.81297700	7.73977300	-0.06431500
C	-0.66872700	8.53893700	-0.17416400
C	0.57998100	7.92995300	-0.29254300
C	0.69716900	6.54143200	-0.28170100
N	-5.67838900	-6.85123500	0.04005400
N	-3.09660800	8.34159000	0.03953300
N	8.77430900	-1.49010700	0.03988700
C	-6.18438600	-7.78455200	-0.87240600
C	-5.85410600	-9.09013300	-0.42721900
C	-5.11817900	-8.93787500	0.81052600
C	-5.02819100	-7.54564400	1.06667000
C	9.83566000	-1.46081800	-0.87243500
C	10.80125400	-0.52257600	-0.42618000
C	10.30120400	0.03767700	0.81190500
C	9.05044200	-0.58069600	1.06733300
C	-3.65377700	9.24585800	-0.87236200
C	-4.94920100	9.61187700	-0.42538700
C	-5.18314200	8.89843600	0.81279200
C	-4.02151000	8.12525600	1.06744000
C	-4.54841000	-9.84319100	1.71350100
C	-3.90995300	-9.35691900	2.85064900
C	-3.84297100	-7.97457900	3.09644000
C	-4.40051300	-7.05189900	2.21379100
C	-6.87745000	-7.57209300	-2.06738000
C	-7.25439300	-8.69173400	-2.80598700
C	-6.94717100	-9.99326300	-2.37303400
C	-6.24564900	-10.19774400	-1.18850300
C	-3.12520200	9.73988500	-2.06820200
C	-3.90787300	10.62561400	-2.80584400
C	-5.18822700	11.00966400	-2.37107400
C	-5.71419900	10.50423000	-1.18578200
C	-6.25070600	8.85696600	1.71733900
C	-6.14661600	8.06109600	2.85442600
C	-4.98210200	7.31274800	3.09864700

C	-3.90555300	7.33496800	2.21443800
C	9.99811000	-2.16597000	-2.06819200
C	11.15627400	-1.93191100	-2.80648900
C	12.12992300	-1.01568800	-2.37245900
C	11.95630800	-0.30714600	-1.18718100
C	10.80009600	0.98317700	1.71563700
C	10.05936700	1.29232300	2.85272100
C	8.82867800	0.65898800	3.09777100
C	8.30870700	-0.28474700	2.21443500
H	0.74786300	-2.14351500	-1.58379200
H	2.96482800	-3.20156100	-1.58934800
H	4.35606800	-0.29905900	1.26117300
H	2.14061200	0.76136600	1.26167500
H	-0.40985900	-2.23489200	1.26106100
H	-2.43668500	-3.62231200	1.26110400
H	-4.25445900	-0.96483000	-1.58823200
H	-2.22917100	0.42499800	-1.58343000
H	1.48270100	1.71811000	-1.58546900
H	1.29067800	4.16687100	-1.59179000
H	-1.91682500	3.92173600	1.26080800
H	-1.72799700	1.47287900	1.26186700
H	-3.67742400	-5.12411900	-0.03102300
H	-7.95083000	-5.46826600	-0.15083400
H	-8.13687800	-2.99457000	-0.36379900
H	-6.10957000	-1.58475300	-0.32922600
H	6.27797600	-0.62132300	-0.03192800
H	8.71354400	-4.14946000	-0.15244900
H	6.66469500	-5.54774600	-0.36680500
H	4.42981900	-4.49754500	-0.33253400
H	-2.59965700	5.74571300	-0.03184000
H	-0.76357200	9.61980900	-0.15378200
H	1.47207100	8.54542100	-0.36978700
H	1.68102900	6.08507400	-0.33566200
H	-4.60882400	-10.91287000	1.53008000
H	-3.46346100	-10.04999300	3.55796800
H	-3.34938300	-7.61453600	3.99518000
H	-4.35573700	-5.98681600	2.41621100
H	-7.11065300	-6.57023200	-2.41249000
H	-7.79544400	-8.55193200	-3.73799800
H	-7.25748200	-10.84511500	-2.97142500
H	-6.00067500	-11.20433200	-0.85946700
H	-2.14132400	9.44131300	-2.41466000
H	-3.51787800	11.02435100	-3.73849400
H	-5.77204600	11.70387600	-2.96877100
H	-6.70817900	10.79482800	-0.85555800
H	-7.14757200	9.44342900	1.53515600
H	-6.96906500	8.02044300	3.56290000
H	-4.91538700	6.70535500	3.99732000
H	-3.00484900	6.76425500	2.41551300
H	9.24696200	-2.86834600	-2.41410600
H	11.30574100	-2.46935500	-3.73908900
H	13.02282200	-0.85793100	-2.97067500
H	12.70553400	0.40799500	-0.85742900
H	11.75672300	1.46580200	1.53279000
H	10.43611000	2.02512800	3.56058500
H	8.26978200	0.90590000	3.99647100
H	7.36386700	-0.77865100	2.41626500

N-Ph-o-Cb, neutral state $E_{\text{total}} = -2991.6758183$ Hartree // B3LYP/6-31G(d)

C	-0.85431400	1.13124200	-0.40025100
N	0.00054500	-0.00216100	-0.42881000
C	-0.55397400	-1.30902400	-0.40092500
C	1.40947900	0.17138500	-0.40117000
C	0.01027100	-2.31502200	0.39861200
C	-0.54874400	-3.58846900	0.42240300
C	-1.69478500	-3.90289700	-0.32658500
C	-2.24901600	-2.88967900	-1.12688600
C	-1.68561600	-1.62004400	-1.17273000
C	2.24478600	-0.65409700	-1.17183400
C	3.62589300	-0.50552100	-1.12775900
C	4.22604800	0.48354900	-0.33042800
C	3.38064900	1.31925300	0.41799800
C	1.99843000	1.16504400	0.39604800
C	-0.55829500	2.26717300	-1.17160900
C	-1.37705500	3.38922700	-1.12589000
C	-2.53210200	3.41471600	-0.32627100
C	-2.83221200	2.26469300	0.42249500
C	-2.00788200	1.14455300	0.39898000
C	5.69823100	0.68514300	-0.29614800
C	-2.25853400	-5.27765500	-0.28902100
C	-3.44218200	4.58928900	-0.28993100
C	6.62288800	-0.37134700	-0.13228800
C	7.99973300	-0.11878100	-0.12941600
C	8.48775800	1.17644700	-0.28446400
C	7.58851000	2.23405900	-0.42569000
C	6.21827800	1.98550200	-0.42796200
C	-3.63638200	-5.54757200	-0.12571500
C	-4.10797100	-6.86555200	-0.11855200
C	-3.23170700	-7.93764100	-0.26891000
C	-1.86566200	-7.69020000	-0.40965300
C	-1.39389800	-6.37998300	-0.41599900
C	-2.98887000	5.91825500	-0.12717000
C	-3.89580300	6.98455800	-0.12256100
C	-5.26189900	6.75989400	-0.27456200
C	-5.72881000	5.45241300	-0.41450700
C	-4.82868600	4.38983500	-0.41861800
N	6.18900100	-1.71812400	0.05850300
N	-4.58453000	-4.49647800	0.06036200
N	-1.60518100	6.21592800	0.06054300
C	-0.85210100	5.93833600	1.20420100
C	0.45840800	6.45319900	1.03076200
C	0.49343300	7.07669000	-0.27598600
C	-0.79939100	6.91641300	-0.83946000
C	6.39179600	-2.76803500	-0.83952500
C	5.88519800	-3.96669300	-0.27280200
C	5.36450700	-3.62193800	1.03394700
C	5.57373300	-2.22915400	1.20411400
C	-5.81868000	-2.82389300	1.02747600
C	-6.37819700	-3.10837100	-0.27774400
C	-5.59479500	-4.15020600	-0.83936900
C	4.76013800	-4.35702800	2.06096700
C	4.38086500	-3.70343900	3.22986900
C	4.60389100	-2.32342900	3.38306800
C	5.20299600	-1.56834000	2.37750900
C	6.96205400	-2.74134200	-2.11550800
C	7.02838100	-3.94218400	-2.81984600
C	6.53755600	-5.14017500	-2.27233300
C	5.96502800	-5.15807000	-1.00314900
C	-7.44928700	-2.58411900	-1.01062300
C	-7.72071500	-3.09478700	-2.27731100
C	-6.92982000	-4.12237800	-2.81988800
C	-5.85732700	-4.66317900	-2.11293800
C	-4.31337300	-2.80431600	3.37627400
C	-5.39591000	-1.92061300	3.21876700
C	-6.15175700	-1.92728100	2.05000700
C	-1.23613500	5.28674900	2.37848500

C	-0.28010500	5.14489500	3.38153100
C	1.02625500	5.64146700	3.22507500
C	1.39978300	6.29690800	2.05535700
C	1.48360000	7.74126900	-1.00883800
C	1.17880200	8.22811900	-2.27731200
C	-0.10548000	8.05437400	-2.82164100
C	-1.11066500	7.39682700	-2.11473100
H	0.88117400	-2.09509200	1.00734400
H	-0.10595200	-4.34483400	1.06501800
H	-3.11564000	-3.10224200	-1.74451100
H	-2.12147400	-0.85905500	-1.81195600
H	1.80391400	-1.41367200	-1.80929000
H	4.24331000	-1.15030400	-1.74479100
H	1.37248700	1.81011000	1.00394800
H	0.31886800	2.26486700	-1.81054900
H	-1.12829700	4.24634800	-1.74323700
H	-3.70913700	2.25851300	1.06442000
H	-2.25252100	0.27988800	1.00721900
H	8.67920300	-0.95406600	0.01174200
H	9.55883600	1.35737300	-0.28234800
H	7.95227400	3.25100400	-0.54456000
H	5.52302600	2.80818800	-0.56791400
H	-5.17146100	-7.03430700	0.02218500
H	-3.61206600	-8.95511300	-0.26361000
H	-1.16794100	-8.51514900	-0.52485600
H	-0.33334500	-6.19134700	-0.55524100
H	-3.51164900	7.99057800	0.01763900
H	-5.95393200	7.59716600	-0.27104600
H	-6.79169500	5.25920600	-0.53099200
H	-5.19409900	3.37646800	-0.55758600
H	4.59407400	-5.42541200	1.94767600
H	3.91215200	-4.26327400	4.03435600
H	4.30457300	-1.83306700	4.30553100
H	5.37378600	-0.50400800	2.50019400
H	7.34397400	-1.81841200	-2.54048500
H	7.46899900	-3.94916700	-3.81319400
H	6.60533300	-6.05954800	-2.84703600
H	5.58358200	-6.08583200	-0.58421400
H	-8.06104300	-1.78709300	-0.59559900
H	-8.55034700	-2.69563300	-2.85394400
H	-7.15660900	-4.50499300	-3.81140600
H	-5.24984100	-5.45804300	-2.53413600
H	-3.73880900	-2.78627500	4.29851100
H	-5.64532200	-1.23029400	4.01974800
H	-6.99309500	-1.24875000	1.93341700
H	-2.24306800	4.90280300	2.50374100
H	-0.55288300	4.64038200	4.30459300
H	1.74746600	5.51514900	4.02769900
H	2.40784300	6.68714100	1.93963400
H	2.47885900	7.87458800	-0.59240300
H	1.93978700	8.74628500	-2.85396200
H	-0.32213200	8.43937100	-3.81450200
H	-2.10195500	7.26621000	-2.53725600
H	3.81409600	2.08296300	1.05829300
C	-4.71830700	-3.70215600	1.20197800
C	-3.96046100	-3.70636200	2.37527000
H	-3.12493900	-4.38680200	2.50141300

N-Ph-2-Th, radical cation $E_{\text{total}} = -2404.923962$ Hartree // UB3LYP/6-31G(d)

C	1.01211437	-0.98410846	0.07111476
N	-0.00012629	-0.00012318	0.07181746
C	0.34592864	1.36849409	0.07107759
C	-1.35839461	-0.38470308	0.07115832
C	-0.39670824	2.29555222	0.83172165
C	-0.04982187	3.63340169	0.83305659
C	1.04084804	4.11723363	0.07022421
C	1.77125772	3.17233626	-0.68872419
C	1.44026616	1.82975608	-0.68826838
C	-2.30509420	0.33238062	-0.68813955
C	-3.63330092	-0.05222022	-0.68847739
C	-4.08639264	-1.15715396	0.07057411
C	-3.12200224	-1.85973554	0.83341283
C	-1.78993521	-1.49129423	0.83193737
C	0.86444446	-2.16249409	-0.68821369
C	1.86173108	-3.12034392	-0.68876212
C	3.04529964	-2.96014731	0.07005635
C	3.17157580	-1.77369874	0.83293081
C	2.18632625	-0.80444263	0.83170762
C	1.38508549	5.52783005	0.07597168
C	-5.48011784	-1.56431961	0.07638694
C	4.09497315	-3.96336356	0.07548131
C	0.64234133	6.59296553	0.56229684
C	1.27623326	7.84869626	0.40442106
C	2.50542509	7.74755837	-0.19961707
S	2.90531974	6.11328117	-0.58534366
C	-6.03135934	-2.73949031	0.56407339
C	-7.43573168	-2.81861153	0.40581914
C	-7.96254023	-1.70434704	-0.19990819
S	-6.74703861	-0.54142769	-0.58683498
C	5.38868718	-3.85267509	0.56206286
C	6.15956444	-5.02919751	0.40355029
C	5.45774671	-6.04292525	-0.20127899
S	3.84241681	-5.57228004	-0.58696253
H	-1.22062473	1.94948547	1.44655499
H	-0.61183574	4.31617847	1.46059828
H	2.59525194	3.50363788	-1.31310687
H	2.00201888	1.13342566	-1.30149893
H	-1.98298621	1.16698931	-1.30145854
H	-4.33223314	0.49576058	-1.31281089
H	-3.43225887	-2.68781495	1.46100742
H	-1.07825593	-2.03178339	1.44675904
H	-0.01947882	-2.30092327	-1.30140203
H	1.73665893	-3.99959098	-1.31315348
H	4.04398634	-1.62825761	1.46031137
H	2.29863215	0.08214769	1.44649094
H	-0.34216517	6.48027379	1.00171925
H	0.84212054	8.79039549	0.71987621
H	3.20130125	8.54174626	-0.43577764
H	-5.44170296	-3.53512275	1.00488374
H	-8.03431344	-3.66498083	0.72223885
H	-8.99818170	-1.49913652	-0.43673112
H	5.78304684	-2.94390091	1.00211571
H	7.19213097	-5.12402649	0.71910771
H	5.79790635	-7.04241212	-0.43806432

N-Ph-3-Th, radical cation $E_{\text{total}} = -2404.917917$ hartree // B3LYP/6-31G(d)

C	1.01912747	-0.97885513	-0.01115028
N	-0.00767586	-0.00928737	0.01995663
C	0.31853969	1.36514104	0.03552285
C	-1.36087102	-0.41403731	0.03529482
C	-0.42209985	2.26599649	0.82662464
C	-0.09429834	3.61091648	0.83984167
C	0.97264633	4.12079757	0.06659068
C	1.70368569	3.20105697	-0.71945008
C	1.39101214	1.85380584	-0.73885926
C	-2.32904983	0.30129463	-0.69944863
C	-3.65204502	-0.10170647	-0.68061258
C	-4.07454427	-1.22542140	0.06571697
C	-3.09088122	-1.92527578	0.79983229
C	-1.76225782	-1.53680532	0.78661827
C	0.87735769	-2.14503721	-0.78963440
C	1.88955180	-3.08899480	-0.81794162
C	3.07842239	-2.92274615	-0.07281610
C	3.20176783	-1.74609324	0.70084678
C	2.20111016	-0.79183783	0.73503709
C	1.30261792	5.54734235	0.08103535
C	-5.47493926	-1.65284160	0.07934187
C	4.13724569	-3.93368917	-0.10291673
C	0.92385482	6.46538910	1.12481861
C	1.34769284	7.73985323	0.89752628
S	2.21117044	7.87057504	-0.60460210
C	2.01277767	6.19242127	-0.91775120
C	-6.06873720	-2.48204839	1.09698781
C	-7.38717681	-2.74230355	0.87445164
S	-7.94944912	-1.99851364	-0.59175027
C	-6.40031151	-1.31926409	-0.89559850
C	4.30112428	-4.91787176	-1.14228512
C	5.36045218	-5.74806018	-0.93213631
S	6.18807714	-5.37008681	0.54815931
C	5.10778134	-4.07407216	0.87505771
H	-1.23643822	1.89920511	1.44214262
H	-0.68193915	4.28403693	1.45460137
H	2.53921895	3.55109655	-1.31653741
H	1.95858247	1.17296597	-1.36401989
H	-2.03010254	1.15762918	-1.29424090
H	-4.37952066	0.47062251	-1.24662379
H	-3.37333917	-2.79466313	1.38354140
H	-1.03071589	-2.08311349	1.37218814
H	-0.01821393	-2.29093203	-1.38390934
H	1.75444143	-3.97927545	-1.42249613
H	4.10548768	-1.57477218	1.27625906
H	2.31556639	0.09394318	1.35047286
H	0.39092693	6.17726875	2.02332837
H	1.21772560	8.61049411	1.52591850
H	2.38978656	5.77442342	-1.84101816
H	-5.54235268	-2.83641988	1.97544647
H	-8.06906414	-3.31543360	1.48791317
H	-6.23743065	-0.74617659	-1.79799804
H	3.67701449	-4.97764482	-2.02617957
H	5.71563749	-6.55240843	-1.56193674
H	5.21434954	-3.50974852	1.79127341

N-Ph-p-Cb, radical cation $E_{\text{total}} = -2991.476981$ Hartree // B3LYP/6-31G(d)

C	-1.41079438	0.11767234	-0.00247618
N	-0.00057238	0.00009020	-0.00266247
C	0.60274056	-1.27996516	-0.00234844
C	0.80634443	1.16260562	-0.00256890
C	1.75442860	-1.52901504	0.76738799
C	2.34118129	-2.78495632	0.76248368
C	1.81218626	-3.84624648	-0.00160795
C	0.65711411	-3.57906948	-0.76609194
C	0.06194239	-2.32709498	-0.77173329
C	1.98328835	1.21786510	-0.77238417
C	2.77005462	2.35919702	-0.76682505
C	2.42437046	3.49297712	-0.00194089
C	1.24099225	3.42045979	0.76251879
C	0.44654741	2.28443515	0.76746705
C	-2.20242187	-0.75465945	0.76775731
C	-3.58347209	-0.63468613	0.76275617
C	-4.23797773	0.35364976	-0.00200379
C	-3.42894051	1.21979632	-0.76702031
C	-2.04712475	1.10915700	-0.77248936
C	3.26498734	4.70322861	-0.00140971
C	2.44036432	-5.17917682	-0.00113566
C	-5.70640752	0.47626435	-0.00166441
C	4.65959835	4.62534559	-0.18837774
C	5.45661708	5.76146556	-0.18329223
C	4.88162116	7.03024400	0.00000406
C	3.49182361	7.12624194	0.18244282
C	2.70521253	5.98286845	0.18618086
C	1.67590197	-6.34832509	-0.18728962
C	2.26178162	-7.60641087	-0.18227144
C	3.64826004	-7.74226813	0.00008731
C	4.42597376	-6.58633023	0.18177400
C	3.82862204	-5.33364798	0.18557747
C	-6.33654793	1.72273880	-0.18925171
C	-7.71900592	1.84457763	-0.18436443
C	-8.53004229	0.71210723	-0.00067009
C	-7.91798604	-0.53924849	0.18242899
C	-6.53446525	-0.64844411	0.18633288
N	5.68501363	8.18658408	0.00081731
N	4.24851301	-9.01594903	0.00082576
N	-9.93318715	0.82929670	-0.00004747
C	5.63112814	9.22623735	0.94673604
C	6.59566624	10.20545842	0.60440715
C	7.26002118	9.74469627	-0.60009494
C	6.67884523	8.49958835	-0.94408754
C	5.17667576	-9.48842457	0.94624727
C	5.54290139	-10.81323833	0.60398390
C	4.81106752	-11.15885659	-0.59995689
C	4.02254552	-10.03347602	-0.94367951
C	-10.80651757	0.26295821	0.94606225
C	-12.13690368	0.60801736	0.60341151
C	-12.07020030	1.41320898	-0.60145340
C	-10.70132317	1.53278868	-0.94534775
C	4.84857774	9.34175839	2.09898544
C	5.02189150	10.47725391	2.88940465
C	5.95700957	11.46748128	2.55037764
C	6.75216009	11.33370517	1.41303814
C	8.26341787	10.28562914	-1.40750428
C	8.66681731	9.58820279	-2.54529619
C	8.06505773	8.36682281	-2.88596949
C	7.06075404	7.80761898	-2.09678318
C	-13.04049553	2.01098371	-1.40923562
C	-12.63835701	2.70868034	-2.54730279
C	-11.27973284	2.79856914	-2.88787990
C	-10.29315891	2.20914475	-2.09832616
C	-10.51517163	-0.47184055	2.09871321
C	-11.58514675	-0.88951652	2.88918649
C	-12.91033846	-0.57546419	2.54982813

C	-13.19219128	0.17940486	1.41209792
C	5.66841101	-8.86793699	2.09802227
C	6.56603379	-9.58510647	2.88801792
C	6.95651395	-10.88992379	2.54903302
C	6.44266495	-11.51221126	1.41218632
C	4.77787881	-12.29847848	-1.40709925
C	3.97145296	-12.29978565	-2.54436730
C	3.21379297	-11.16842189	-2.88480738
C	3.23157910	-10.01889121	-2.09587795
H	2.16509947	-0.74074834	1.38944660
H	3.20148122	-2.96059534	1.40047913
H	0.24512437	-4.35468703	-1.40381257
H	-0.80727206	-2.14236063	-1.39408257
H	2.25765658	0.37280892	-1.39494457
H	3.64752902	2.39022427	-1.40485403
H	0.96328011	4.25320258	1.40080318
H	-0.44124873	2.24595034	1.38981176
H	-1.72520505	-1.50414272	1.39026432
H	-4.16580369	-1.29144143	1.40116529
H	-3.89454247	1.96403599	-1.40524258
H	-1.45245865	1.76917523	-1.39516847
H	5.13597299	3.65500553	-0.28944471
H	6.53297540	5.67130254	-0.28240360
H	3.03168573	8.10341001	0.28199812
H	1.62957851	6.09063794	0.28667305
H	0.59727793	-6.27613012	-0.28762520
H	1.64577490	-8.49373147	-0.28071548
H	5.50239170	-6.67599159	0.28067987
H	4.45948900	-4.45572844	0.28545650
H	-5.73461786	2.62057305	-0.29062700
H	-8.17933139	2.82165518	-0.28391819
H	-8.53395841	-1.42643006	0.28231341
H	-6.08974426	-1.63370291	0.28730043
H	4.13831279	8.57345171	2.38354523
H	4.42307265	10.59132531	3.78832001
H	6.06800085	12.34083049	3.18589941
H	7.48847388	12.09245501	1.16336819
H	8.71762488	11.24004820	-1.15655136
H	9.44706550	9.99741704	-3.17988380
H	8.38137576	7.84629279	-3.78521139
H	6.58852123	6.87431150	-2.38259118
H	-14.09414469	1.92684109	-1.15835462
H	-13.38298232	3.17921495	-3.18218470
H	-10.98720393	3.33246999	-3.78733613
H	-9.24877951	2.26709794	-2.38409166
H	-9.49461753	-0.70226310	2.38353717
H	-11.38443501	-1.46463467	3.78840744
H	-13.72213223	-0.91603122	3.18539908
H	-14.21751120	0.43718580	1.16216551
H	5.35779264	-7.86877388	2.38250731
H	6.96458052	-9.12312970	3.78656279
H	7.65808111	-11.42218519	3.18420778
H	6.73200722	-12.52915012	1.16255895
H	5.37794324	-13.16867718	-1.15635437
H	3.93576988	-13.18026531	-3.17873881
H	2.60428154	-11.18259908	-3.78366176
H	2.65882530	-9.14361215	-2.38151476

N-Ph-m-Cb, radical cation $E_{\text{total}} = -2991.469723$ Hartree // B3LYP/6-31G(d)

C	-1.18128938	0.78288443	-0.17469516
N	-0.00090035	0.00030886	-0.17476970
C	1.26703832	0.63131467	-0.17513201
C	-0.08839679	-1.41325155	-0.17419248
C	2.32230533	0.11626895	-0.94970074
C	3.56234889	0.73878685	-0.94460483
C	3.80360832	1.89412274	-0.17584264
C	2.73643611	2.39844443	0.59280017
C	1.49261953	1.78388023	0.59952326
C	0.79714037	-2.18436983	0.60079729
C	0.70773891	-3.56885011	0.59479100
C	-0.26248678	-4.24144907	-0.17344632
C	-1.14269333	-3.45537450	-0.94247302
C	-1.06217329	-2.07017733	-0.94815846
C	-1.26325368	1.95414114	-0.94944937
C	-2.42253462	2.71660092	-0.94412867
C	-3.54336365	2.34787258	-0.17482967
C	-3.44614892	1.17171011	0.59401939
C	-2.29186276	0.40202737	0.60051826
C	-0.34998409	-5.71866359	-0.17747565
C	5.12698711	2.55629011	-0.18020272
C	-4.77880310	3.16240701	-0.17925173
C	0.80862584	-6.50442661	-0.07024330
C	0.73037684	-7.90039227	-0.07536580
C	-0.51533232	-8.53314512	-0.19653112
C	-1.66857554	-7.75976723	-0.31595671
C	-1.59178894	-6.36885214	-0.30422713
C	5.22909202	3.95242094	-0.07213732
C	6.47755387	4.58187703	-0.07728394
C	7.64788784	3.81879580	-0.19932610
C	7.55379451	2.43354743	-0.31983634
C	6.31044896	1.80535278	-0.30812893
C	-6.03869819	2.55223932	-0.07141895
C	-7.20840708	3.31820920	-0.07729100
C	-7.13327593	4.71326778	-0.20001769
C	-5.88676674	5.32492312	-0.31998147
C	-4.72072641	4.56276668	-0.30736882
N	1.91008742	-8.67721093	0.03914559
N	-8.47103977	2.68529614	0.03831311
N	6.56127559	5.99179610	0.03830890
C	2.31457891	-9.68337257	-0.84883879
C	3.54410028	-10.22568315	-0.39714963
C	3.89688133	-9.51609133	0.81821372
C	2.86939363	-8.56840500	1.05550912
C	7.23086653	6.84559088	-0.84893851
C	7.08685819	8.18119108	-0.39586637
C	6.29622833	8.13125352	0.81966784
C	5.98839036	6.76755603	1.05568767
C	-9.54499886	2.83711361	-0.84947001
C	-10.62934755	2.04421425	-0.39630272
C	-10.19078793	1.38526373	0.81963595
C	-8.85618116	1.80136049	1.05587184
C	4.96363630	-9.61317139	1.71489148
C	4.98944053	-8.77750663	2.83132781
C	3.95466602	-7.85672563	3.06131172
C	2.88000972	-7.73977682	2.18107639
C	1.70661231	-10.12069057	-2.02938753
C	2.33827359	-11.13797864	-2.74287842
C	3.54748942	-11.69801148	-2.30025914
C	4.15805803	-11.24294016	-1.13150083
C	-9.62011832	3.58063160	-2.03106012
C	-10.81722563	3.54141865	-2.74403290
C	-11.90678984	2.77505820	-2.29988633
C	-11.81762316	2.02040038	-1.13009352
C	-10.80793518	0.51105178	1.71758310
C	-10.09671588	0.07209980	2.83423623
C	-8.78179572	0.50802417	3.06320658

C	-8.14348635	1.37914420	2.18168481
C	7.91308523	6.53842794	-2.02996709
C	8.47900304	7.59437854	-2.74246516
C	8.36048136	8.92123895	-2.29848332
C	7.66154595	9.22182015	-1.12929178
C	5.84796964	9.10299552	1.71755762
C	5.11164224	8.70683575	2.83393857
C	4.83080564	7.35025537	3.06264991
C	5.26574191	6.36173560	2.18115262
H	2.15522236	-0.75531703	-1.57366823
H	4.34750956	0.34594314	-1.58298775
H	2.89568702	3.26457049	1.22775741
H	0.69664484	2.17570356	1.22391749
H	1.53429467	-1.69040721	1.22495198
H	1.37836606	-4.13942263	1.22992121
H	-1.87542551	-3.93937431	-1.58057818
H	-1.73358767	-1.49010120	-1.57236316
H	-0.42520825	2.24500747	-1.57396020
H	-2.47529314	3.59284218	-1.58270890
H	-4.27565643	0.87655671	1.22923599
H	-2.23271674	-0.48303885	1.22512334
H	1.78581731	-6.03537691	-0.02656128
H	-0.57184143	-9.61642101	-0.17515803
H	-2.63571189	-8.24679810	-0.39757941
H	-2.50348144	-5.78238933	-0.36274263
H	4.33468962	4.56469652	-0.02782751
H	8.61463106	4.31081159	-0.17781227
H	8.45874015	1.83899866	-0.40227405
H	6.25772042	0.72265024	-0.36745662
H	-6.12123306	1.47149189	-0.02688865
H	-8.04300814	5.30409893	-0.17900602
H	-5.82476415	6.40590814	-0.40269404
H	-3.75688526	5.05880207	-0.36656082
H	5.75876750	-10.33477495	1.54950510
H	5.81355121	-8.84485174	3.53512093
H	3.98634546	-7.22591782	3.94504311
H	2.07447372	-7.03916159	2.37431563
H	0.78085335	-9.68213525	-2.38624844
H	1.88585165	-11.49916900	-3.66178366
H	4.01458205	-12.48964625	-2.87823339
H	5.09987521	-11.67132025	-0.80019951
H	-8.77749663	4.16241530	-2.38913255
H	-10.90407367	4.11253896	-3.66370995
H	-12.82615689	2.76570735	-2.87746141
H	-12.65949235	1.41956830	-0.79759862
H	-11.83052645	0.18315170	1.55301567
H	-10.56687627	-0.60705336	3.53901919
H	-8.25103618	0.16620285	3.94715074
H	-7.13388289	1.72665295	2.37413397
H	7.99528852	5.51773139	-2.38788589
H	9.01769108	7.38367583	-3.66167680
H	8.81305120	9.72180306	-2.87571185
H	7.56258288	10.25139100	-0.79690014
H	6.07602455	10.15240956	1.55321653
H	4.75879345	9.45370446	3.53871013
H	4.26893117	7.06175111	3.94637202
H	5.06124328	5.31372498	2.37338187

N-Ph-o-Cb, radical cation $E_{\text{total}} = -2991.460755$ Hartree // B3LYP/6-31G(d)

C	0.11020235	1.41040718	-0.41737240
N	-0.00244643	0.00176645	-0.43257684
C	-1.27839701	-0.60517678	-0.41792032
C	1.16147716	-0.79943669	-0.41573710
C	-1.51096169	-1.76023862	0.35413283
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